

**Supplementary Figures and Tables for “Fast
Effect Size Shrinkage Software of Beta-Binomial
Models of Allelic Imbalance”**

Figure 1: Distribution of Simulated Effect Sizes from Student's t Simulation
Our sampled distribution gave us mostly very small effect sizes, but with occasional moderate and large effect sizes appearing.

Figure 2: Distribution of Overdispersion Parameter Estimates from Mouse Dataset Gene-specific overdispersion parameters were estimated from fitting intercept-only models to each gene in the mouse dataset.

Quantiles	50th	75th	90th	95th	97.5th	99th	99.5th	Max
Apeglm	0.018	0.055	0.186	0.38	0.640	1.376	3.426	4.729
Ash	0.015	0.066	0.256	0.559	1.059	3.309	4.52	5.85

Table 1: Quantiles of Shrinkage Scores for Normal Simulation

Ash had more extreme shrinkage than apeglm, as evident by larger shrinkage scores across all quantiles above the 50th, particularly at the largest quantiles.

Figure 3: CAT Comparisons after Filtering Out Infinite ML Genes

Results shown are for the normal simulation. mle.filter, apegM.filter and ash.filter remove genes with truly infinite ML estimates prior to analysis.

Quantiles	50th	75th	90th	95th	97.5th	99th	99.5th	Max
Apeglm	0.072	0.171	0.385	0.571	0.791	1.152	1.526	5.78
Ash	0.083	0.189	0.402	0.576	0.805	1.184	1.551	5.811

Table 2: Quantiles of Shrinkage Scores for Student’s T Simulation

Neither method tended to have much more extreme shrinkage than the other in this simulation, though on average ash still shrank more ($p < 0.001$ from a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test).

Evaluation Metric	ML	Apeglm	Ash
75th Percentile of Shrinkage Scores	NA	0.025	0.172
90th Percentile of Shrinkage Scores	NA	0.112	0.351
97.5th Percentile of Shrinkage Scores	NA	0.393	0.773
99th Percentile of Shrinkage Scores	NA	0.649	1.137
Median Summed Counts of Top 50 Genes	10134	10294	10801
Average Interval Width for 95% CI	0.815	0.679	0.058

Table 3: Evaluation Metrics after Removing Genes with Infinite ML estimates
Metrics are for the interaction effect estimates. For each gene, we define the shrinkage score as movement from the ML estimate to zero. The median summed counts over all genes is 6322. ML: Maximum Likelihood, apeglm: Approximate Posterior Estimation of Generalized Linear Model Coefficients, ash: Adaptive Shrinkage.